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**Crossed Wires:
A Signaling Perspective on the Interplay of Venture capitalist and New ventures'
Alliance**

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Abstract:

This paper pivots around the question whether strategic alliances and VC investors complement or substitute each other in nurturing start-ups. While inroads have been made on how venture capitalist and alliance networks affect interorganizational collaboration (e.g. Ozmel, reuer and Gulati, 2013) the effect of VC prominence in determining a new venture's future alliance formation is still largely discarded in the VC and alliance formation literatures. Drawing on signaling theory, we pose that signals on how venture capitalists operate across multiple networks how and alliance networks affect interorganizational collaboration. Then, building on recent contributions to network theory, we argue that the signal will matter more, if the startup nurturing takes place in a high-risk setting. We provide new insights into the incidence of specific VC signals in the context of start-up alliance formation. In addition, we contribute to the emerging literature that takes on behavioral perspective on the interplay of venture capitalist and start-up alliance formation by showing that the 'reputational effect that comes with a VC matters.

Keywords: Venture Capitalists; High-tech industries; Signaling Theory; Market Signaling, Digital Business Models, Effective Strategic alliances, FinTech.

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Background

The literature describes a number of ways in which a firm can collaborate by means of voluntarily initiated cooperative agreements between independent firms that involve exchange, sharing or development (Gulati & Singh, 1998), and venture capitalists (VCs). Notable however, when studying alliances and VCs, scholars tend to look at them separately (Hoenig & Henkel, 2015; Tykvová, 2018).

No prior research has explicitly linked startups' early VC network performance to their founding-network composition. Omzel, for instance, shows that start-ups' increased alliance activity makes future alliances more likely, but future VC activity less likely. Among the many factors potentially impeding collaboration is the risk of adverse selection, which can arise between a new venture and its potential alliance partners when is information asymmetry regarding the value of the new venture's resources and its future prospects.

A first stream of research has looked into the relationship between venture capitalists and their portfolio ventures. In particular, strategy and organizations scholars have long noted that venture capitalists are actively involved in management of the portfolio companies to assure their success (Gifford, 1997). A venture capitalist (VC) is a private equity investor that provides capital to companies exhibiting high growth potential in exchange for an equity stake. This could be funding startup ventures or supporting small companies that wish to expand but do not have access to equities markets. The extant studies show that a new venture's affiliations with prominent intermediaries such as venture capitalists (VCs) signal its quality, suggesting that the new venture has superior resources and capitalists as well as better market opportunities.

Research streams on venture capitalists and alliances are central to the field of entrepreneurial literature but have evolved independently. The extant entrepreneurial literature does little to inform us about how to the interplay between venture capitalists and alliances. Although it is widely acknowledged, there is little empirical research demonstrating such a phenomenon or exploring its theoretical underpinnings. It is this gap that we attempt to address in our study. We employ a signaling perspective in new ventures context.

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Technology-based new ventures

Technology-based new ventures are not representative of the entire population of start-ups, they form an important subgroup, particularly with regard to their contribution to the respective national economy, job creation and innovation (Almus & Nerlinger, 1999; Audretsch, 1995). Due to the critical challenge of linking technological expertise with market-related capabilities, these ventures are typically founded by teams (Roberts, 1999) whereby the question of retaining and updating plays a particularly pertinent role, making technology-based new venture teams an interesting context to study evolution and performance effects of new venture teams.

Extant studies provide evidence on how venture capital (VC) investment affects startup firms' alliance formation and performance. Despite the rich and abundant research on the relationship between VC investment and startup's alliance, there is no clear evidence about the contribution of VC investment on the performance and market value of invested firms.

The Financial Stability Board of the Bank for International Settlements defines fintech as “technologically enabled financial innovation that could result in new business models, applications, processes, or products with an associated material effect on financial markets and institutions and the provision of financial services” (European Banking Authority 2017, p. 4).

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The research project will be conducted in collaboration with TechQuartier, which was founded in 2016 in Europe's financial center of Frankfurt, is a cross-industry innovation platform created to bring new ventures, corporates and new talent together to work, meet, learn and collaborate on new technologies and digital business models. Its member-based community numbers more than 300 new ventures, 50 academic and corporate innovators and hundreds of potential founders. TechQuartier, with nine other major European hubs, boosts the international connection of FinTech new ventures and scale-ups. The ten major European hubs represent over 1,500 FinTechs in total.

Venture capitalists and the evolution of entrepreneurial firm' strategic alliance

We explore how venture capitalist (VC) withdrawal adversely affects the focal new ventures' alliances (Phelps, 2010). Using a network approach, we investigate how new ventures maintain strategic alliances by enlisting prestigious interlocking directorates regardless of VC withdrawal deter new prospective investors and how interlocking directorates moderate the negative relationship between VC withdrawal and start-ups' alliances.

Strategic alliances play a central role in scaling new ventures at different stages. We use the classic definition of strategic alliances as "voluntary arrangements between firms involving exchange, sharing, or co-development of products, technologies, or services. They can occur as a result of a wide range of motives and goals, take a variety of forms, and occur across vertical and horizontal boundaries (Gulati, 1998)." Past findings in entrepreneurship literature have shown that the contributions of venture capitalists (VC) to new ventures' alliance formation (Zhang, Jiang, Wu, & Li, 2019) are positively correlated. (Hallen, Davis, & Murray, 2020). VC firms have also been found to facilitate tie transitivity with other ventures through the formation of R&D alliances (Reuer & Devarakonda, 2017). Whereas existing research focuses more on how VC positively affect the development of new ventures' equity and social capital, however, other researchers have recently explored the potential negative consequences of venture capitalist investment withdrawals (Cox Pahnke, McDonald, Wang, & Hallen, 2015; Hernandez, Sanders, & Tuschke, 2015). Thus, in this study, we consider the negative

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influences across different interfirm networks and investigate how venture capitalists (VC) withdrawal affects the evolution of new ventures' strategic alliances. We argue that the non-repetition of ties with venture investors could potentially increase the tension and impede new ventures' alliances when "the VC terminates its relationship with the new ventures" (Shafi, Mohammadi, & Johan, 2020). In addition, this study addresses a topic that we do not yet fully understand, namely, how new ventures manage their alliances strategically to alleviate concerns of misappropriation in venture capitalist withdrawal. We seek to provide effective strategies to alleviate the significant potential negative impact by non-repetition of investment ties to the new ventures.

Venture capitalist provides a unique context where we can examine how a VC adjusts its decision over time based on updated information at each round of financing, which is the focal concern of dynamic real options theory (Bowman and Hurry, 1993; Trigeorgis, 1996). Many investment projects of strategic importance, such as R&D, are undertaken in discrete stages, but such staged financing is usually unobservable to researchers. In addition, a study of venture capitalist withdrawal is important in its own right because of venture capitalist's important role in financing entrepreneurship. Many of the high tech icons, such as Microsoft, Apple, Cisco Systems, and Genentech, have been venture backed in their early stages. Research studies and industry reports suggest that venture capitalist has contributed substantially to job creation, innovation, and economic growth in the United States (Global Insight, 2007; Kortum and Lerner, 2000).

For new ventures in high-tech industries, two critical types of networks are networks of prior alliances, or alliance networks (e.g., Baum et al., 2000), and VC syndicate networks, which are formed through VCs' joint investments in new ventures (Sorenson & Stuart, 2001). Even though previous research has extensively analyzed the impact of alliance networks on future alliance formation (e.g., Gulati, 1998, 1999; Gulati & Gargiulo, 1999), it has devoted far less attention to the impact of other important types of networks, such as VC syndicate networks. This represents an important omission since VCs are critical providers of resources (e.g., Bygrave & Timmons, 1992; Gompers & Lerner, 2000) and certify the quality of new ventures (e.g., Gulati & Higgins, 2003;

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Hsu, 2006). Therefore, to have a more complete understanding of the determinants of alliance evolution of new ventures, we need to investigate the implications of a new venture's affiliations with VCs.

Our hypothesis pertains to new ventures experiencing VC withdrawing. While prior literature focuses more on venture capitalists (VC) firms' withdrawals from VC syndicates are associated with their subsequent syndication, we flip the focus around and shift attention to new ventures' perspective on how such disruptive consequences of such terminations on new ventures' other interfirm relationships' stability. Specifically, we seek to exploit the consequences of VC withdrawal and to determine whether their structure and characteristics explain the new ventures' alliance evolution and termination. Prior work has found that the features and salient position of VC can lead to various benefits in new ventures' interfirm networks. In an attempt to depart from prior research dominantly focus on the advantage of VC network ties, we are planning to examine the costs of VC withdrawal (VC non-repetition of ties). We conjecture VC withdrawal might deteriorate to the strategic alliances of new ventures.

Extant research show that network resources are significant to a firm's choice of partner selection (Meuleman, Lockett, Manigart, & Wright, 2010; Ozmel, Reuer, et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2012). New ventures often utilize the existing VC investment partners to form direct and indirect connections with other potential investors or alliance partners. Some scholars find that the VCs are active to help new ventures' alliance development (Blevins & Ragozzino, 2018). Another study shows that an increased probability that two firms pair in an alliance if they share a common venture capitalist investor (Lindsey, 2008). In contrast, a recent study suggests that the withdrawal of VC firms can poison the relationships among their portfolio companies and abandoned co-investors (Guler, 2007). Sullivan and his colleagues found the evidence that "the spread of negative information" can lead to interfirm network partners leaving and overall network structure changing (Sullivan, Haunschild, & Page, 2007). The negative signals generated by the exit decisions in early-stage firms of VC could undermine the focal firm's reliability. The strategic alliances' partners of the focal entrepreneurial firm

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also face the adverse selection risk to continue the existing interfirm partnership (Polidoro Jr, Ahuja, & Mitchell, 2011). Therefore, we argue VC withdrawal increases the chance of unplanned dissolution of new ventures' alliance and this effect is stronger for high status and reputable VC firm, which are more visible in the network. When at least one of the existing VCs withdrew from the follow-on round of financing, we coded the observation related to that round of investment as VC withdrawal.

Fombrun defined reputation as “a perceptual representation of a company's past actions and prospects that describes the firm's overall appeal to all its key constituents when compared to other leading rivals. (Fombrun & Rindova, 1996, p. 32)”. Here, we use the classic definition of “reputation” as “a set of attributes ascribed to a firm, inferred from the firm’s past actions” (Weigelt & Camerer, 1988: 443). The entrepreneurs are much more willing to be invested and affiliated by high-reputation VCs (Hsu, 2004). the better the reputations of participating venture capitalist firms and strategic alliance partners were, the more money a startup raised, and the larger was the size of a startup's network of strategic alliances.

Nonetheless, “a withdrawal from a high-reputation VC may have broader repercussions; namely, implications for the exchange partner’s reputation for reliability.”

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No firm initially had a superior reputation, network, or funding. A firm may have different reputations with different stakeholders, who may have different perceptions of “highly valued outcomes”.

In this study, we will employ quantitative data to build a panel dataset. We form the panel dataset by combining information from various data sources, including CrunchBase (www.CrunchBase.com) (Ter Wal, Alexy, Block, & Sandner, 2016), ThomsonOne and Security Data Corporation (SDC) database (Pollock, Lee, Jin, & Lashley, 2015; Wang, 2020). Our data include U.S. and European new ventures that received VC funding from 2007 to 2016 (Colombo, 2016 #471). Recent research has shown that the activities of VC are fundamentally different in young new ventures may vary across countries (Colombo & Shafi, 2016). Thus, we will test our ideas in a research context of the United States and the Europe. In sum, we will focus on the young new ventures’ alliances evolution and study their reaction to the changes catalyzed by VC. A period of time (10 years) will be considered for data collection.

Conclusion

In sum, our study contains several implications for theory and practice. We contribute to the studies the dilemmas that new ventures face when accessing equity and social capital in several ways. First, our primarily to the literature on entrepreneurship literature by identifying uncertainty drives organizations to interact with their existing VC partners that navigates the prevalent discontinuation of investment relationships. Second, we emphasize the importance of understanding the extent to when an entrepreneurial firm opts for a new prestigious interlocking directorate as a lever for effective strategic change.

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Our research also has some implications for new ventures and the VC partners they choose. New ventures need to be careful about choosing their partner(s) to avoid the uncertainty that put their long term interfirm relationship at risk of losing opportunities to develop and grow. Overall, we add insights to the network and signaling literature and to the nascent literature on how the early discontinuation of investment relationships could negatively impact an entrepreneurial venture's other interfirm relationships.

Overall, we add insights to the network and signaling literatures and to the nascent literature on how strategic action, especially by low-power actors such as entrepreneurs, shapes critical network outcomes.

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